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GENOMED4ALL

D9.2

Interim Communication & Dissemination report

GENOMED4ALL receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D9.2

Interim Communication & Dissemination report

Revision **v1.1**

Work package	WP9
Task	T9.2
Due date	30-09-2022
Submission date (updated version)	16-02-2024
Deliverable lead	AUS – AUSTRALO
Version	v1.1
Authors	Diana López (AUS)
Reviewers	Anna Rizzo (DW), Mar Mañú (VHIR)

Abstract

This document provides a comprehensive overview of all dissemination and communication actions undertaken to reach a critical mass throughout GenoMed4All's first review period (M1-M18) and has been updated to include all new developments up until M36. It contains a detailed description of the project's visual identity, online channels, promotional materials, events and publications, together with an introduction to its onboarding and networking strategies.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Impact, Engagement, Promotion, Consultation

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	09-09-2022	First working draft	Diana López (AUS)
v0.2	19-09-2022	Advanced draft ready for internal review	Diana López (AUS)
v0.3	22-09-2022	Internal review completed by VHIR	Mar Mañú (VHIR)
v0.4	26-09-2022	Internal review completed by DW	Anna Rizzo (DW)
v1.0	27-09-2022	Final version ready for submission	Diana López (AUS)
v1.1	16-02-2024	<p>New version with updates from M21 onwards. History of changes/updates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Updated timeline references in section 1.1, 3 and 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Updated KPIs in section 2.1 <input type="checkbox"/> Screenshots and metrics in section 3.2. <input type="checkbox"/> New materials in section 3.3. <input type="checkbox"/> List of publications in section 3.4 <input type="checkbox"/> List of events in section 3.5 <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration with SYNTHEMA in section 4.3.5 <input type="checkbox"/> New training details in section 4.4 <input type="checkbox"/> Associate Members Onboarding Handbook in section 4.5 	Diana López (AUS)

Disclaimer

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme**Nature of the deliverable**

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC**CO** Confidential to GenoMed4All project and Commission Services*** Deliverable types:****R:** document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).**DEM:** demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.**DEC:** websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.**OTHER:** software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDS	Haematological diseases
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
RHDs	Rare Haematological Diseases
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable intends to act as an update and in-depth review of GenoMed4All's strategy and framework conceived for **Communication, Dissemination and Engagement** purposes.

The initial design of this framework was previously outlined in GenoMed4All's **Impact Master Plan** (D9.1), during the early stages of the project. Now comes the time to reflect on the outreach efforts carried out through this first review period and study its overall performance.

Thus, the present document provides a comprehensive recap of the Communication and Dissemination timeline, tools and methodology, together with detailed descriptions of every action that has been put in place so far in order to:

- ❑ Effectively **promote the project and its results** in any public forum (e.g. events, conferences, webinars...), either on a participant role or as hosts.
- ❑ Accurately **disseminate the results available**, both to the scientific communities within our clinical and technical spheres and the general public, making GenoMed4All's achievements easily understood and widely accessible to a non-expert audience.
- ❑ Maintain **dedicated communication channels** that are open, active and engaging in the way they inform and educate about the project: keeping our target audiences up to date on our ambition, work plan and GenoMed4All's day-to-day.
- ❑ Start drafting our vision for GenoMed4All's **long-term sustainability**, in the form of solid **onboarding and engagement strategies** that can become the starting point for external third parties (other clinical sites, research institutions, EU initiatives, associations...) to join GenoMed4All and become end users of our platform in the future.

In keeping with these high-level goals, this deliverable has been structured as follows:

- ❑ **Section 1** is the **Introduction**, where the purpose and scope of the document are outlined.
- ❑ **Section 2** is concerned with the **Dissemination & Communication strategy**, where a bird's eye view of the outreach timeline and performance is presented.
- ❑ **Section 3** explains the **Communication & Dissemination activities implemented**, where more details are given on specific actions, highlights and metrics.
- ❑ **Section 4** details the **Engagement strategy**, where all efforts regarding onboarding of external parties and community building are presented in detail.
- ❑ **Section 5** outlines the **Conclusions** of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

It is no secret that a significant part behind the long-term success of disruptive innovation depends on the level of awareness it can effectively raise and the overall engagement it is able to create. Designing and executing an effective dissemination and communication strategy, its results and achievements can gain widespread attention and persist far beyond the project's initial run.

Therefore, a solid dissemination and communication strategy should be geared towards ensuring the active involvement of key stakeholders in the project to establish a committed community that can network opportunities for future developments.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable (**D9.2 – Communication & Dissemination Interim report**), is presented in the framework of GenoMed4All's **WP9 – Impact, Outreach and Collaboration**, specifically within task **T9.1 – Dissemination and communication plans**.

This report provides an overview of all key activities and actions related to communication and dissemination that took place during the first 18 months of the project, and has been updated to also include the overview up to the end of the second official periodic report (M36). It gives an analytic presentation of the performance of our digital channels, participation in physical and online events, publications online articles...

The initial strategy for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation was presented in deliverable **D9.1 – GenoMed4All Impact Master Plan**, submitted in M6. D9.2 is the second entry in the list of WP9 deliverables and intends to highlight the progress of the project's outreach and engagement strategies during the first review period (M1-M18). As mentioned, the contents of this document have been expanded upon and updated accordingly to reflect the status at the end of the second review period (M19-M36). A final revision will be included in the upcoming D9.4, the project's final report on Communication and Dissemination activities.

2 Dissemination & Communication strategy

GenoMed4All's **overall outreach goals** are to:

- ❑ Increase general awareness and interest about the project to build a solid customer base/ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- ❑ Communicate technical, scientific results and benefits to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- ❑ Deliver top-level messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- ❑ Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of GenoMed4All to reach the widest possible community.

As previously outlined in GenoMed4All's Impact Master Plan, communication activities have been planned in 3 different phases (**Plan & Revisit**, **Early bird communication** and **Targeted communication**), which are closely related to dissemination as well. The common goal was to build and nurture a community and brand around the project, to maximize visibility and engage with end users to foster dialogue and collect feedback on the project's vision and progress.

Figure 1. Phases of GenoMed4All's outreach plan

In this regard, the **timeline** followed has been the following:

- ❑ During the first 6 months of the project (**Plan & Revisit** phase) the visual identity and key brand assets of the project have been created, all Communication & Dissemination channels have been set up and the first mapping of stakeholders has been completed.
- ❑ From M6 to M12 (**Early bird communication**), the focus progressively shifted towards establishing a recognizable presence in all our digital channels, begin the conversation with

related initiatives and start working on additional promotional materials and long-form articles to cover core concepts of the project for a wider audience.

- ❑ From M12 to M18, efforts have gone into increasing our event participation and publications, beginning to brainstorm and draft GenoMed4All's value proposition and refining our engagement strategy for onboarding new clinical sites and research institutions in the future.
- ❑ From M19 to M36 (as of the last update to this deliverable) GenoMed4All's C&D plan is officially in its **Targeted Communication** phase. The goal now is to keep building our presence in digital channels, reinforcing our core messages and linking them to upcoming results, such as the first iteration of GenoMed4All's business plan (due by the end of 2022). GenoMed4All is now in its fourth and final execution year. As such, careful planning will go into boosting our dissemination and engagement efforts, with a view to maximize the project's visibility and impact and ensure its long-term sustainability.

2.1 Performance review

In this 36-month period, the project has managed to consolidate its **online presence**, mobilizing a total of **1.6K followers** in social media (see *Section 3.2*), keeping up a meaningful, steady stream of daily content with **1K+ posts** in social media, **36 blog entries** and **15 Zenodo publications** overall.

This promotional effort has been boosted by an increased participation in key **events, conferences and webinars** (due in great part to the relaxation of Covid-19 restrictions for face-to-face meetings). GenoMed4All has organized and hosted **8 webinars and workshops** and been present in **25 featured events** and **5 webinars/workshops** during this timeframe (see *Section 3.5 for more details*). The consortium's commitment to dissemination is also commendable: **30 peer-reviewed publications** have been published so far (see *Section 3.4 for more details*).

Of course, all these actions have been supported by a harmonized branding identity and a solid set of **promotional materials** (see *Section 3.3*), both in print (e.g. brochures, stickers, factsheets, flyers...) and digital form (e.g. videos, banners, slide decks).

The detailed list of GenoMed4All's **impact KPIs**, together with the updated targets at this point in time, is shown in the following table. A detailed breakdown of the project's metrics (e.g. website, social media) are provided in the dedicated sections addressing GenoMed4All's digital channels below.

Type	Indicators	Target	Current
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals	20	17
Publications	Peer-reviewed publications and presentations in international conferences	20	13

Publications	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g. articles, blog posts) (yearly)	75	1,000+
Events	No. scientific & non-scientific events participated	25	25
Workshops	No. webinars/workshops organized	5	8
Workshops	No. participants (total)	200	320+
Website	No. unique visitors	1000	3,271
Printed material	No. hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	3,000	500
Social media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	6,000	1,626
Social media	No. impressions (monthly average)	600	8,960
Videos	No. videos produced	3	6
Videos	No. visits (by the end of the project)	3,000	532
Newsletters	No. newsletters contributed/released	15	18

Table 1. GenoMed4All's KPI tracker

3 Communication & Dissemination activities implemented

3.1 Visual identity

3.1.1 Logo and brand assets

GenoMed4All's complete visual identity was designed and presented during the first months of the project. This includes the project's **visual guidelines**, **branding assets** (logo variations, icons, banners), **typography** and **color codes** that are shown below.

The GENOMED4ALL logo is shown centered on a horizontal banner with a color gradient from dark blue on the left to light blue on the right. The text 'GENOMED4ALL' is white, with the 'O' containing the DNA helix icon.

Figure 2. GenoMed4All – Main logo

FONT

Cabin

abcdefghijklmnop
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download [here](#)

FONT

Raleway

abcdefghijklmnop
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

PRIMARY

#4c4b9f
RGB 76, 75, 159

#16d8d8
RGB 22, 216, 216

SECONDARY

#0d2956
RGB 13, 41, 86

#e6227f
RGB 230, 34, 127

NEUTRAL

#444444
RGB 68, 68, 68

#e6e6f6
RGB 230, 230, 246

Figure 3. Typography and color codes for GenoMed4All

Figure 4. GenoMed4All – different logo and color variations

Figure 5. GenoMed4All – Banners (light/dark variations)

3.1.2 Official templates

As a way of harmonizing all documentation and resources coming from GenoMed4All, several official templates have been produced for the project's deliverables (Word) and presentations (PowerPoint).

3.2 Online channels

The idea behind GenoMed4All's **Communication & Dissemination toolkit** is to build and maintain a portfolio of all the digital channels and accounts that have been set up for the promotion and uptake of results from the project.

This toolkit includes: the project's official website and social media (X/Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube), a Zenodo repository for Open Access publications and other online platforms, like Brevo.

Figure 6. Overview of GenoMed4All's C&D toolkit

3.2.1 Project website

Website

www.genomed4all.eu

GenoMed4All's website is the main entry point showcasing the project's main ideas and approach, news, findings and results from our use cases (MDS – Myelodysplastic Syndromes, MM – Multiple Myeloma and SCD – Sickle Cell Disease).

Figure 7. GenoMed4All's website – Home page

Figure 8. GenoMed4All’s website – content tree

In terms of performance, the breakdown from the site’s metrics on Google Analytics is presented below. This overview spans the project’s run so far and shows the aggregated totals from the official launch of GenoMed4All’s website (February 2021) to the present moment. During the 36-month period under consideration, the website has driven a traffic of **88 average monthly users**, achieved a total of **12,693 pageviews** and attracted **3,271 unique users**, of which **13% are returning visitors** interested in keeping up to date with the project’s overall progress.

Figure 9. Overview of GenoMed4All’s website analytics

3.2.2 Social media

X/Twitter	@genomed4all
LinkedIn	/genomed4all

GenoMed4All maintains an active presence in **X/Twitter** and **LinkedIn**, with an aggregated audience of **1.6K followers** between both platforms. Social media is a quick and effective way to directly engage with the project’s wider audience and other key related initiatives, as well as to promote GenoMed4All’s achievements in terms of publications, events and partners’ initiatives.

Figure 10. GenoMed4All – Twitter profile and timeline

Figure 11. GenoMed4All – LinkedIn company page

The project's **performance overview on social media** is presented below, together with our engagement metrics (impressions and page views) for both channels in the execution period so far (up to M36).

Looking at our online presence in detail, the project benefits from a very active community of **1,626 followers (1,011 in X/Twitter and 615 in LinkedIn)**. Overall, GenoMed4All's social media channels attract a steady flow of followers and direct engagement **every month: on average, 43 new followers** join our online community each month, generating **8.9K impressions** a month when interacting with our content (either through liking, sharing or commenting our posts) and triggering a total of **1.2K page views**.

Figure 12. Overview of GenoMed4All's social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) and performance metrics for latest quarter (Q4 2023)

3.2.2.1 Social media campaigns

Our strategy on social media follows a mixed recipe combining two different sets of ingredients:

- ❑ First, high-level information about the project and the team behind it, packaged into easy-to-digest **general campaigns** that use flashcards and attractive visuals to communicate the main vision, mission and expertise driving GenoMed4All.
- ❑ Second, the design and execution of **targeted campaigns** around key milestones (e.g. featured events, meetings or achievements of note, other relevant dates to keep in our editorial calendar).

To further illustrate this, several examples of GenoMed4All’s social media campaigns are presented below.

Figure 13. Examples of GenoMed4All’s general outreach campaigns – About the project and Partner features

Figure 14. Examples of GenoMed4All's targeted outreach campaigns – Rare Disease Day 2022 and GenoMed4All at Expo Dubai

Figure 15. Examples of latest campaigns (from left to right, top to bottom): AI in Healthcare/Digital Healthcare news, Network content and Media updates, Project updates, Weekly quiz, Quote of the week

These are both critical building blocks of an effective social media presence, as they have a direct impact on the interactions and engagement the project can build (see figure below) and also let us modulate our key messages to reach a broader audience, while staying relevant to GenoMed4All's target stakeholders' needs and expectations.

Figure 16. GenoMed4All's social media campaigns and their impact on engagement (snapshot from Jan-Apr 2022)

3.2.3 Zenodo

Zenodo

www.zenodo.org/communities/genomed4all-h2020/

Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, GenoMed4All provides open access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, brand assets and other resources generated within the project, as per our Data Management Plan.

There is a dedicated Zenodo community and repository already in place for the project, where all sorts of publications (e.g. articles, posters...), public deliverables, press releases and more can be found.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for the GENOMED4ALL H2020 Project. The top navigation bar includes the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for Communities and My dashboard. The main header features the GENOMED4ALL logo and the project name, along with a 'New upload' button. Below the header, a search bar indicates '15 results found' and a 'Sort by' dropdown is set to 'Newest'. The left sidebar contains filters for Versions, Access status, Resource types, and Subjects. The main content area displays three records:

- D4.1 - Hybrid Federated Learning model** (January 27, 2022, v1): Project deliverable, Open, 15 results. Authors: Silvia Uribe, Javier Serrano, Alberto del Rio, and 2 others. Description: The main aim of this deliverable is to define GenoMed4All's hybrid federated learning model specification expressed in terms of platform requirements, which have been acquired by analyzing in details the project's objectives as well as by decomposing the stakeholders' needs through the different use cases' definition. It includes a description o... Uploaded on April 12, 2023.
- D2.2 - First Report of the Ethics Advisory Board** (February 2, 2022, v1): Project deliverable, Open, 27 results. Author: Nathan Lea, Dipak Kairia. Description: This deliverable provides the first report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). The report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022. The meeting was presented with the current position with regards the project objectives and progress, data protection and ethics oversight and as... Uploaded on April 12, 2023.
- GenoMed4All - Project presentation AUSTRALO** (May 19, 2022, v1): Presentation, Open, 16 results. Description: The second slide deck produced for GenoMed4All. The presentation is meant to reflect the contents of the project's first official video presentation. Uploaded on September 19, 2022.

Figure 17. GenoMed4All – Open Access community at Zenodo

3.2.4 Brevo – GenoMed4All's internal check-in

GenoMed4All's **internal check-in** was created as a means to reinforce the project's internal communication channels and make them more engaging. The goal was to have a series of internal mailing campaigns to keep everyone updated on the project's overall progress and news.

Our tool of choice is the [Brevo](#) platform, where we periodically design, prepare and send out campaigns for everyone involved in GenoMed4All (so far, **18 campaigns** have already been sent).

Figure 18. Email campaigns from GenoMed4All's internal check-in

3.3 Promotional materials

During this period, the following **batch of promotional material** has been produced. So far, this effort includes the creation of two project slide decks, a tri-fold brochure, flyers, a project factsheet, stickers and the launch of GenoMed4All's first official video presentation. Additionally, on-going support has been provided for *ad hoc* graphic design, multimedia and other on-demand assets for specific events and promotional actions, which are presented below.

Figure 19. Overview of GenoMed4All's promotional materials

3.3.1 Slide decks

Slide decks serve as one of the entry points for GenoMed4All and they convey an effective and visually attractive introduction to the project: our main vision, scope, targets and team.

GenoMed4All's first slide deck is available through the project's open access community at Zenodo ([here](#)). A second slide deck reflecting the contents of the project's first video presentation has also been made available [here](#).

Figure 20. GenoMed4All's first slide deck

Figure 21. GenoMed4All's second slide deck

3.3.2 Tri-fold brochure, flyers and stickers

As part of GenoMed4All branded merchandise, printed materials like brochures and stickers have been designed and made available in digital format, to be printed out when required (e.g. for display in events and conferences). Physical copies have been handed out at key events, like the Expert Workshop on AI for Health during Expo Dubai or the EHA annual hybrid congress.

Figure 22. GenoMed4All's tri-fold brochure

Figure 23. Sticker designs for GenoMed4All

Figure 24. Flyer design for GenoMed4All

3.3.3 Videos

YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/@genomed4all>

GenoMed4All maintains a dedicated **YouTube** channel as a way to upload and share workshop recordings, official introductory videos and/or any other multimedia content produced throughout the project's run. The channel currently hosts the recording from the first instalment in our first webinar series ([Webinar #1 – Introduction to Genomics and Data processing](#)), the [project's official presentation video](#), all the recordings from our training programme's first wave - [GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large](#) (see [Section 4.4](#) for further details) and video recap for our latest General Assembly in Barcelona.

Figure 25. GenoMed4All's official video presentation

Figure 26. GenoMed4All – Official YouTube channel

3.3.4 Factsheet

Meant as a straightforward way of providing a quick, to-the-point overview of the project, GenoMed4All's factsheet is a two-page condensed introduction to our main use cases, technologies, partners and targets.

Figure 27. GenoMed4All's factsheet

3.4 Publications

These two review periods have shown a slow but steady dedication from the consortium towards building and maintaining a publishing pipeline for GenoMed4All's peer-reviewed publications (both clinical and technical). The complete list is presented below and covers everything from scientific articles, papers and clinical studies to approved abstracts and posters in international conferences.

3.4.1 Scientific publications

Type	Title	Authors	Platform
Article	A Sex-Informed Approach to Improve Prognostication and Personalized Decision-Making Process in Myelodysplastic Syndromes	G. Maggioni, E. Travaglino, A. Pierola et al	Blood Journal
Article	Protein Stability Perturbation Contributes to the Loss of Function in Haploinsufficient Genes	G. Birolo, S. Benevenuta, P. Fariselli, E. Capriotti, E. Giorgio, T. Sanavia	Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences
Article	Classification and Personalized Prognostic Assessment on the Basis of Clinical and Genomic Features in Myelodysplastic Syndromes	M. Bersanelli, E. Travaglino, M. Meggendorfer, T. Matteuzzi, C. Sala, E. Mosca, C. Chiereghin, N. D. Nanni et al	Journal of Clinical Oncology
Clinical study	GENOMED4ALL: Improving MDS Classification and Prognosis by AI	Istituto Clinico Humanitas	ClinicalTrials.gov
Article	Clinical relevance of clonal hematopoiesis in the oldest-old population	M. Rossi, M. Meggendorfer, M. Zampini et al	Blood Journal
Article	Effectiveness of Biologically Inspired Neural Network Models in Learning and Patterns Memorization	L. Squadrani, N. Curti, E. Giampieri, D. Remondini, B. Blais, G. Castellani	Entropy Journal
Conference poster	GenoMed4All: Artificial Intelligence-based Deep Learning algorithms for patients with Sickle Cell Disease	A. Idrizovic, S. van der Veen, M.D.M Mañu, A. Collado, R. Colombatti, M.P. Boaro, P. Bartolucci, M. de Montalembert et al.	IUBMB Focused Meeting – Hemoglobin Switching Conference
Conference poster	2,3-diphosphoglycerate detection via direct infusion high-resolution mass spectrometry correlates	S. van der Veen, M.J. van Dijk, J.J.M. Jans, N.M. Verhoeven-Duif, R. van	EHA2022 Congress

	<u>with quantitative detection in blood patients with SCD</u>	Wijk, M. Bartels, M.D.M. Mañú Pereira, R. Colombatti et al.	
Conference paper	<u>Radiomics and artificial intelligence for identification and monitoring of silent cerebral infarcts in sickle cell disease: first analysis from the GENOMED4ALL European project</u>	R. Biondi, M.P. Boaro, N. Biondini et al	Abstract Book for the 27th EHA Congress
Conference poster	<u>Integrative diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease patients for Personalized Medicine</u>	A. Idrizovic, A. Collado, E.J. van Beers, R. Colombatti, P. Bartolucci, M. de Montalembert, M.P. Boaro, D. Beneitez, A. Ortuño, A. Ruiz, I. Isola, E. Cela, R. van Wijk, M. Rab, M.D.M. Mañú	4 th Global Congress on Sickle Cell Disease
Article	<u>Multi-Modal Analysis and Federated Learning Approach for Classification and Personalized Prognostic Assessment in Myeloid Neoplasms</u>	S. D. Amico, L. D. Olio, C. Rollo, P. Alonso, I. Prada-Luengo, D. D. Olio, C. Sala, M. Bersanelli, E. Sauta, M. Bicchieri, P. Morandini, T. Tommasini, V. Savevski et al	ASH2022
Article	<u>Random walk approximation for stochastic processes on graphs</u>	S. Polizzi, T. Marzi, T. Matteuzzi, G. Castellani, A. Bazzani	MDPI Entropy
Article	<u>Challenges and Opportunities of Precision Medicine in Sickle Cell Disease: Novel European Approach by GenoMed4All Consortium and ERN-EuroBloodNet</u>	A. Collado, M. P. Boaro, S. van der Veen, A. Idrizovic, B. J. Biemond, D. Beneitez Pastor, A. Ortuño, E. Cela, A. Ruiz-Llobet, P. Bartolucci, M. de Montalembert et al.	HemaSphere
Article	<u>Real-world Validation of Molecular International Prognostic Scoring System (IPSS-M) for Myelodysplastic Syndromes</u>	E. Sauta, M. Robin, M. Bersanelli, E. Travaglino, M. Meggendorfer, L. Zhao et al.	Journal of Clinical Oncology
Article	<u>DrOGA: An Artificial Intelligence Solution for Driver-Status Prediction of Genomics</u>	M. Bastico; A. Fernández-García; A. Belmonte-Hernández; S. Uribe et al.	IEEE Access

<u>Mutations in Precision Cancer Medicine</u>			
Article	<u>The need for multimodal health data modeling: A practical approach for a federated-learning healthcare platform</u>	F. Cremonesi, V. Planat, V. Kalokyri, H. Kondylakis, T. Sanavia, V. M. Mateos, B. Singh, S. Uribe et al.	Journal of Biomedical Informatics
Article	<u>Covering hierarchical Dirichlet mixture models on binary data to enhance genomic stratifications in onco-hematology</u>	D. D. Olio, E. Sträng, A. T. Turki, J. M. Tettero, M. Barbus, R. Schulze-Rath, J. Martinez, T. Matteuzzi, A. Merlotti, L. Carota, C. Sala, M. G. D. Porta et al.	PLOS Computational Biology
Article	<u>Synthetic Data Generation by Artificial Intelligence to Accelerate Research and Precision Medicine in Hematology</u>	S. D. Amico, D. D. Olio, C. Sala, L. D. Olio, E. Sauta, M. Zampini et al.	JCO Clinical Cancer Informatics
Article	<u>Sickle cell disease landscape and challenges in the EU: the ERN-EuroBloodNet perspective</u>	M. D. M. Mañú, R. Colombatti, F. Alvarez, P. Bartolucci, C. Bento, A. L. Brunetta, E. Cela, S. Christou, A. Collado et al.	The Lancet Hematology
Article	<u>Opportunities and Challenges of Synthetic Data Generation in Oncology</u>	F. Jacobs, S. D'Amico, C. Benvenuti, M. Gaudio, G. Saltalamacchia, C. Miggiano, R. De Sanctis, M.G. Della Porta, A. Santoro, A. Zambelli	JCO Clinical Cancer Informatics
Clinical study	<u>GenoMed4ALL: Improving SCD Classification and Prognosis by AI</u>	Hospital Universitari Vall d'Hebron Research Institute	ClinicalTrials.gov
Conference paper	<u>Scalable and portable federated learning simulation engine</u>	B. Arroyo, J. Mata, S. Uribe	ACM Digital Library
Conference paper	<u>Federated learning for causal inference using deep generative disentangled models</u>	A. Almodóvar, J. Parras, S. Zazo	Deep Generative Models for Health Workshop @ NeurIPS 2023
Conference paper	<u>Clinical and Genomic-Based Decision Support System to Define the Optimal Timing of Allogeneic Hematopoietic Stem</u>	C. A. Tentori, C. Gregorio, M. Robin, N. Gagelmann, C. Gurnari, S. Ball, J. C. Caballero Berrocal, L. Lanino, S. D'Amico, M.	ASH 2023

	<u>Cell Transplantation in Patients with Myelodysplastic Syndromes</u>	Spreafico, G. Maggioni, E. Travaglino, E. Sauta et al.	
Conference paper	<u>Clinical Text Reports to Stratify Patients Affected with Myeloid Neoplasms Using Natural Language Processing</u>	G. Asti, E. Sauta, N. Curti, G. Carlini, L. Dall'Olio, L. Lanino, G. Maggioni, A. Campagna et al.	ASH 2023
Conference paper	<u>Synthetic Histopathological Images Generation with Artificial Intelligence to Accelerate Research and Improve Clinical Outcomes in Hematology</u>	G. Asti, S. D'Amico, N. Curti, G. Carlini, E. Sauta, N. R. Derus, D. Dall'Olio et al.	ASH 2023
Conference paper	<u>Combining Gene Mutation with Transcriptomic Data Improves Outcome Prediction in Myelodysplastic Syndromes</u>	E. Sauta, M. Zampini, D. Dall'Olio, C. Sala, G. Todisco, E. Travaglino, L. Lanino et al.	ASH 2023
Conference paper	<u>Data-Driven Harmonization of 2022 Who and ICC Classifications of Myelodysplastic Syndromes/Neoplasms (MDS): A Study By the International Consortium for MDS (icMDS)</u>	L. Lanino, S. Ball, J. P. Bewersdorf, M. Marchetti, G. Maggioni, E. Travaglino, N. H. A. Ali, P. Fenaux, U. Platzbecker, V. Santini, M. Diez-Campelo et al.	ASH 2023
Conference paper	<u>Ensemble of Heterogeneous Machine Learning Models with Multiple Inputs for Multi Omics Analysis</u>	E. Trivizakis, V. Koutoulidis, L. A. Mouloupoulos, E. Terpos, I. Ntanasis-Stathopoulos, P. Malandrakis, P. Grigoropoulos et al.	IEEE EMBS International Conference on Data Science and Engineering in Healthcare, Medicine & Biology, 2023
Conference paper	<u>Fully Automated Detection and Segmentation Pipeline for the Bone Marrow of the Lytic Bone of Multiple Myeloma Patients</u>	E. Koutoulakis, E. Trivizakis, V. Koutoulidis, L. A. Mouloupoulos, E. Terpos, I. Ntanasis-Stathopoulos, P. Malandrakis, P. Grigoropoulos et al.	IEEE EMBS International Conference on Data Science and Engineering in Healthcare, Medicine & Biology, 2023

Table 2. List of GenoMed4All's peer-reviewed Open Access publications

All publications from GenoMed4All (e.g. articles, papers, approved public deliverables so far, posters, clinical trials) can be found and linked in a dedicated section of our website – [Publications](#).

Figure 28. GenoMed4All website – Publications

3.4.2 Awareness publications

GenoMed4All's consortium has also been quite active and enthusiastic in the production of non-scientific publications. In this regard, there is a **dedicated News section** in the project's website, which currently displays **36 news pieces** ranging from press releases, publications, webinars to general project updates.

3.4.2.1 Articles and blog posts

Of note in this category are GenoMed4All's **Knowledge Pills**: carefully crafted long-form articles covering core concepts of the project in a thorough but accessible manner. So far, 3 installments have been published in this series, with a great response from both the consortium and our audience as a whole.

- ❑ **Knowledge Pill #1:** [Machine Learning in Healthcare – a brief introduction.](#)
- ❑ **Knowledge Pill #2:** A conversation on Federated Learning – [Part 1](#) and [Part 2](#).

Another knowledge pill addressing GenoMed4All's **end-to-end business architecture** is currently in the works.

Figure 29. Overview of GenoMed4All's collection of Knowledge Pills

3.4.2.2 Press releases and more

The first press release for the project's launch was published in February 2021 and is accessible through [Zenodo](#) and the [News](#) section on the project's website.

3.5 Events, conferences and workshops

Taking into consideration the delicate situation for face-to-face gathering brought forward by the Covid-19 pandemic and the subsequent travel restrictions that have gone into effect, GenoMed4All's partners have made a tremendous effort to participate in several scientific and technical events during these 18 months. Overall, GenoMed4All has been prominently featured in **6 events** and **4 webinars and workshops**.

3.5.1 Featured events

Event	Date	Details	Location	Participants
EBN Annual progress meeting #1	20-05-2021	GenoMed4All was featured in the periodic progress meetings for ERN-EuroBloodNet members (here)	Online	140+ 140+
EBN Annual progress meeting #2	28-10-2021	GenoMed4All was featured in the periodic progress meetings for ERN-EuroBloodNet members (here)	Online	140+ 140+
Expert Workshop on AI for Health at Expo Dubai	17-03-2022	Invitation from InTouchAI.eu to participate in the EU AI Week at Expo Dubai	Dubai (AE)	200+
IUBMB Focused Meeting – Hemoglobin Switching	05-05-2022	Poster showcase by the SCD team: Artificial Intelligence-based Deep Learning algorithms for patients with Sickle Cell Disease (here)	Crete (GR)	80+
EBN Annual progress meeting #3	19-05-2022	GenoMed4All was featured in the periodic progress meetings for ERN-EuroBloodNet members (here)	Online	100+
EHA2022	09-06-2022	Poster showcases at the Annual Congress from the European Hematology Association	Vienna (AT)	15,000+
4th Global Congress on SCD	16-06-2022	Poster + presentation at the reference congress for SCD	Paris (FR)	500+
European Conference on Rare Diseases 2022	30-06-2022	Participation in expert panel on “How to make the best use of ERNs and improve	Online	800+

		efficiency of the whole system”		
XXIX Jornadas Nacionales de Innovación y Salud en Andalucía	06-10-2022	Partner Dedalus presented GenoMed4All at JISA2022	Málaga (ES)	
EBN Annual progress meeting #4	07-11-2022	GenoMed4All was featured in the periodic progress meetings for ERN-EuroBloodNet members (here)	Online	150
ASH annual meeting & exposition 2022	10-12-2022	GenoMed4All participated with a poster + oral presentation (here)	New Orleans (US)	25,000+
Standardization meeting on Lorrca Oxygenscan data for SCD	28-03-2023	SCD team meeting in Utrecht to discuss standardization on Lorrca Oxygenscan data	Utrecht (NL)	20
International Neurovascular Training Course on Sickle Cell Disease	30-03-2023	GenoMed4All was featured as part of a presentation on: <i>European Collaborative Projects for Radiomics in SCD: Genomed4all and SYNTHEMA</i> (here)	Padua (IT)	52
simFALTA - Sickle Cell Disease & Thalassemia symposium	29-05-2023	GenoMed4All was featured as one of ERN-EuroBloodNet’s projects on rare anemias (here)	Madrid (ES)	
ERN-EuroBloodNet Research Meeting at EHA 2023	08-06-2023	A dedicated session for ERN-EuroBloodNet, featuring GenoMed4All (here)	Frankfurt (DE)	70
1ª Jornada de la Asociación Española de Enfermedad de Células Falciforme - ASAFE meeting	17-06-2023	GenoMed4All was featured as one of ERN-EuroBloodNet’s projects (here)	Madrid (ES)	30
XIII SITE Annual Congress	21-09-2023	Italian Society for Thalassemia and Hemoglobinopathies	Rome (IT)	
Italian AIEOP Annual Congress	02-10-2023	Presentation by Raffaella Colombatti on AI for hematology-oncology	Bologna (IT)	

MYNERVA AIRC Meeting	12-10-2023	Periodic progress meeting for AIRC “MYNERVA” project, involving GenoMed4All activities	Castiglione del Lago (IT)	
ESAAM 2023	17-10-2023	GenoMed4All was featured as part of the presentation: <i>Federated Learning Simulation Engine</i> (here)	Ludwigsburg (DE)	
50th SIE Annual Congress	23-10-2023	Italian Society of Hematology	Roma (IT)	
EBN Annual progress meeting #5	09-11-2023	GenoMed4All was featured in the periodic progress meetings for ERN-EuroBloodNet members (here)	Online	127
IEEE EMBS 2023	07-12-2023	International Conference on Data Science and Engineering in Healthcare, Medicine & Biology	Malta (MT)	
ASH annual meeting & exposition 2023	09-12-2023	GenoMed4All participated with several papers and an oral presentation (here)	San Diego (US)	32,081

Table 3. List of GenoMed4All featured events

Figure 30. Featured events (from left to right, top to bottom): EBN progress meeting #1, Expert Workshop on AI for Health at Expo Dubai, IUBMB Focused Meeting – Hemoglobin Switching, EHA2022, Global Congress on SCD 2022, ECRD2022, Dedalus at JISA2022, EBN progress meeting #4, ICH at ASH2022, Lorrca standardization meeting, International Neurovascular Training Course on SCD, ERN-

EuroBloodNet Research Meeting at EHA2023, ASAFE meeting, Joint internal workshop with SYNTHEMA, Italian AIEOP Annual Congress, ESAAM 2023, EBN progress meeting #5, IEEE EMBS 2023, ASH 2023

3.5.2 Workshops and webinars

Webinar/Workshop	Date	Details	Location	Participants
An Introduction to Genomics and Data Processing	14-04-2021	1 st GenoMed4All webinar (here)	Online	40+ (hosted by GenoMed4All)
Patient Engagement workshop	30-09-2021	A meeting with MDS, MM and SCD European patients' associations	Online	70+ (hosted by GenoMed4All)
GenoMed4All: AI and Genomics	18-05-2022	Webinar on AI applied in Genomics for Personalized Medicine in Haematological Diseases	Online	50+
"Data sharing in health research projects" webinar	23-05-2022	Roundtable discussion on data sharing in research hosted by KATY , one of our sister projects	Online	50+
HPC training (2 sessions)	24-01-2023	Internal training sessions from CINECA on practical HPC aspects and applications for GenoMed4All	Online	40+ between both sessions (hosted by GenoMed4All)
ENROL Webinar for patients: 1. Networking on European Registries in Rare Hematological Disorders	15-02-2023	GenoMed4All was featured as one of ERN-EuroBloodNet's projects	Online	
GenoMed4All at ETSISI UPM	24-02-2023	GenoMed4All was presented at ETSISI UPM (computer science and SW engineering degree).	Madrid, Spain	110+
GenoMed4All and ERN-EuroBloodNet for precision medicine in hematology	13-09-2023	GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large (Wave 1, Session #1)	Online	107 registered, 50+ attended (hosted by ERN-EuroBloodNet + GenoMed4All)
Use cases challenges – MDS, SCD and MM	27-09-2023	GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet	Online	86 registered, 40+ attended

		<u>Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large</u> (Wave 1, Session #2)		(hosted by ERN-EuroBloodNet + GenoMed4All)
<u>Joint internal workshop SYNHEMA-GenoMed4All</u>	28-09-2023	Collaboration and synergies between GenoMed4All and SYNHEMA	Online	30+
<u>Data standardization and linkage (standards and federation)</u>	04-10-2023	<u>GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large</u> (Wave 1, Session #3)	Online	67 registered, 30+ attended (hosted by ERN-EuroBloodNet + GenoMed4All)
<u>ASCAT 2023 - The 18th Annual Sickle Cell and Thalassaemia Conference</u>	27-10-2023	ERN-EuroBloodNet session: Workshop on application of Artificial Intelligence for SCD (here)	London, UK	
<u>Data integration and analysis (Artificial Intelligence)</u>	08-11-2023	<u>GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large</u> (Wave 1, Session #4)	Online	103 registered, 50+ attended (hosted by ERN-EuroBloodNet + GenoMed4All)

Table 4. List of GenoMed4All's workshops and webinars

Figure 31. Webinars and workshops (from left to right, top to bottom): Introduction to Genomics and Data Processing, Patient Engagement Workshop, GenoMed4All: AI and Genomics webinar, “Data sharing in health research projects” webinar, HPC training sessions, GenoMed4All at ETSISI UPM, GenoMed4All and ERN-EuroBloodNet training programme, ASCAT 2023

Key events (e.g. conferences, congresses, webinars/workshops, training) are showcased through a dedicated section on our website – [Events](#). Each event comes with a companion piece recapping interesting insights, results or publications from the project that were featured in it.

Figure 32. GenoMed4All website – Events

4 Engagement strategy

During the project's first 18 months, efforts linked to community building have focused on the design of GenoMed4All's **engagement and onboarding strategy**, supported by dedicated events like our own **Patient Engagement e-workshop** and the development and analysis of **online surveys** to assess data requirements and potential new clinical sites for GenoMed4All (e.g. General survey on Clinical and Genetic data, Fact finding survey for data protection risk assessment, Associate Member Form).

In this second review period, engagement efforts have continued on through **GenoMed4All's educational program**, a joint enterprise in close collaboration with ERN-EuroBloodNet. All this work has ultimately culminated into the conceptualization and drafting of the project's **Associated Members Onboarding Handbook**, which is introduced in further detail below.

Networking and liaising with advocate initiatives at EU level has also taken a prominent role during this period. In this regard, the project has effectively kicked off conversations with the **ERN-EuroBloodNet** community of practice and other EU-funded initiatives, like **B1MG**, **HARMONY** and **HARMONY+** and GenoMed4All's **sister projects** ([KATY](#), [PANCAIM](#), [INTERVENE](#)) and actively liaising with like-minded projects operating in AI and hematology, like [SYNTHEMA](#)).

4.1 GenoMed4All's Patient Engagement e-Workshop

GenoMed4All's Patient engagement e-workshop has been one of the cornerstones of the project's engagement strategy. This online workshop, conceived as a meeting with MDS, MM and SCD European patients' associations, intended to provide an overview of GenoMed4All's mission, clinical pilots and relevant AI use-case applications to representatives of major patients' associations in Europe covering the 3 clinical areas related to the project.

The meeting was a joint effort by GenoMed4All consortium and ERN-EuroBloodNet: it gathered **70+ registrants** and speakers from the [Thalassemia International Federation](#), [Myeloma Patients Europe](#), the [MDS Alliance](#) and [EURORDIS](#).

Our wish is to continue the conversation on patient-centricity to gather feedback, unmet needs and expectations on how to involve patients' advocates in the development of clinical AI tools. All the information about the event description and agenda can be found in the [project website's event archive](#).

Figure 33. Snapshots from GenoMed4All's Patient Engagement e-Workshop

Welcome to the e-workshop: GenoMed4All – A meeting with Myelodysplastic Syndromes, Multiple Myeloma and Sickle Cell Disease European patients' associations.

The aim of this meeting is to provide an overview of GenoMed4All's mission, clinical pilots and relevant AI use-case applications to representatives of major patients' associations in Europe covering Myelodysplastic Syndromes, Multiple Myeloma and Sickle Cell Disease, the 3 clinical areas related to the project. The meeting is organised by the GenoMed4All consortium, in collaboration with ERN-EuroBloodNet.

The meeting will be held on Thursday, September 30th 2021, 6:00 PM – 7:30 PM CET.

Figure 34. Official landing page for GenoMed4All's Patient Engagement e-workshop

4.2 Surveys and consultations

As part of GenoMed4All's engagement and onboarding strategy, a series of online surveys have been designed and made available online to kick-off the prospection work on available data sources, necessary ethics approvals and data sharing agreements that are integral to onboarding additional external organizations to GenoMed4All in the future.

4.2.1 Fact finding survey for data protection risk assessment

As a means to support the ground work conducted within **WP2 – Ethical, legal, and data protection framework, including user AI trust**, a dedicated online form was created to support external members willing to participating in GenoMed4All and guide them through all necessary regulatory compliance. Thus, the questionnaire covered the lawfulness of their processing primarily, including the current state of ethics approvals and where they may need to seek amendments from ethics committees to approve participation in GenoMed4All.

The image displays a digital survey form for GenoMed4All. The top banner features the logo and tagline 'Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare'. The survey is divided into sections, with 'Section 1 of 8' and 'Section 3 of 8' visible. Section 1 contains a title, a welcome message, a request for participation, a description of the survey's purpose, and contact details for Nathan Lea. It also includes an email input field and a note about email collection. Section 3 contains a title, a description field, and two multiple-choice questions: 'Does this project have the approval of your relevant Ethics Board(s)?' and 'Have you collected informed consent from the research subjects?'. The form is presented in a clean, modern interface with a dark blue header and light grey content areas.

Figure 35. Snapshot from GenoMed4All's Fact finding survey for data protection risk assessment

4.2.2 General survey on Clinical and Genetic data

This survey was conceived as the initial reference point to assess the availability of data among partners and potential data sources for SCD in the context of the GenoMed4All project. It was circulated among ERN-EuroBloodNet's member community and the clinical networks of GenoMed4All's dedicated SCD team.

GENOMED4ALL
Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

Sickle Cell Disease - General survey on Clinical and Genetic data

Welcome!

This is a survey to assess the availability of data among partners and potential data sources in the context of the GenoMed4All project (www.genomed4all.eu).

You will find questions about potential data sources on Sickle Cell Disease (demographic data, clinical and laboratory parameters, radiological and genomic data...), the format in which they are collected and stored at your center and their overall availability.

Your participation in this survey is greatly appreciated and it will help us immensely in our mission to forward research and fight against health data silos in Haematological Diseases. As a collaborator, we can offer you academic credit, both through our official website and the publications that will be produced throughout the project's lifetime. Also, you will benefit from first-hand information and access to the specific tools and algorithms that we are working hard to develop within GenoMed4All.

* Required

Email address *

Your email

About GenoMed4All

GENOMED4ALL
Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

The European initiative to transform the response to **Haematological Diseases** by seizing the power of **Artificial Intelligence**

A quantum leap in advanced precision medicine, pooling genomic/ -omics' health data through a secure and trustworthy **Federated Learning** platform.

Disclaimer
GENOMED4ALL receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

Please note that all data collected through this online form will only be used for internal research purposes within the GenoMed4All consortium and will not be shared and/or reproduced externally.

Figure 36. Snapshot from GenoMed4All's SCD survey on clinical and genetic data

4.2.3 Associated Member form

Building on the feedback gathered from these previous surveys, GenoMed4All's Associate Member form has been carefully designed to guide potential external organizations (i.e. Associate Members) through the onboarding process to join GenoMed4All, while collecting detailed information about their demographic data, clinical and laboratory parameters, radiological and genomic data, the format in which they are collected and stored at each center and their overall availability.

In return for their collaboration, associate members are offered academic credit, both through our official website and the publications that will be produced throughout the project's lifetime. Also, they will benefit from first-hand information and future access to the specific tools and algorithms developed within GenoMed4All.

Associate Member form

Which of these use cases are you interested in? *

Select all that apply

- Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS)
- Multiple Myeloma (MM)
- Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)
- Other use case

↓ Next

**Alignment to
GenoMed4All
use cases**

No. patients
Use case type
(retrospective/
prospective)
Reference materials

How would you like to be involved with GenoMed4All on the MDS use case?

You wish to... *

Select all that apply

- Access data from GenoMed4All on MDS
- Contribute data to GenoMed4All on MDS

↓ Next

Involvement

**Access data
Contribute data**

**Ethics approvals &
data sharing consents**

What types of data would you be able to contribute? *

Select all that apply

- Demographic data
- Clinical parameters
- Laboratory parameters
- Imaging data
- GWAS data
- Genomic data
- Biobank samples
- Other

↓ Next

**Data
types**

Demographic data GWAS data
Clinical parameters Genomic data
Lab parameters Biobank samples
Imaging data Other

Figure 37. Overall structure and building blocks from GenoMed4All's online Associate Member form

4.3 Networking opportunities

Figure 38. Overview of current networking opportunities

4.3.1 Onboarding new ERN-EuroBloodNet clinical sites

ERNs are virtual networks involving healthcare providers across Europe. They aim to facilitate discussion on complex or rare diseases and conditions that require highly specialised treatment, and concentrated knowledge and resources. Among the 24 ERNs currently operating, GenoMed4All is closely tied to [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), the ERN in **Rare Haematological Diseases** (RHD). Since 10 partners from GenoMed4All are already full members of ERN-EuroBloodNet, our first engagement efforts start with these community of practice, which currently stands at 96 members. As of now, 2 of these clinical sites (one from Belgium, one from the United Kingdom) are already in the process of onboarding GenoMed4All.

4.3.2 Partnering with B1MG – Beyond 1M Genomes

From the very beginning of the project, GenoMed4All has been expected to collaborate closely with funded projects under topic [Beyond 1M Genomes](#) (B1MG) project. B1MG is helping create a network of genetic and clinical data across Europe. The project provides coordination and support to the [1+ Million Genomes Initiative](#) (1+MG).

Currently, GenoMed4All stands as one of the official partner projects for the B1MG initiative. For our project, the opportunity in this collaboration is to contribute to addressing technical specifications and standards for the secure access and exchange of cross-border genomic and other health data, as outlined in the 1+MG roadmap, and explore the ramifications on the ethics, legal and social issues (ELSI) of data sharing.

4.3.3 Clustering with sister projects

Another clear mandate for GenoMed4All in the networking front was to establish a fluent communication with our sister projects funded under the topic **DT-TDS-04-2020: AI for Genomics and Personalised Medicine**:

- ❑ **INTERVENE** – International consortium for integrative genomics prediction.
- ❑ **KATY** – Knowledge At the Tip of Your fingers: Clinical Knowledge for Humanity.
- ❑ **PANCAIM** – Pancreatic cancer AI for genomics and personalized Medicine.

All four projects operate in the intersection of Artificial Intelligence, genomics, precision medicine and patient-centric care. So far, these synergies have materialized on a round-table discussion about cross-cutting issues on data sharing in health research projects. This joint workshop was hosted by the KATY project this past May. It was also a great opportunity to explore different views on Federated Learning and platform infrastructure alternatives.

4.3.4 Exploratory meeting with HARMONY and HARMONY+

The HARMONY Alliance is a Big Data initiative to improve outcomes for patients with blood cancers. The common thread with GenoMed4All, apart from the obvious link to our use cases on MDS and MM (both hematological malignancies), comes from the fact that some of our partners already have a role within HARMONY.

During our first exploratory meeting, several avenues for collaboration were discussed in light of HARMONY's available data sources (10,000 datasets from registries and clinical trials) and its current work on MDS as a disease on focus. Opportunities for collaboration include a preliminary data check and dataset explanation to integrate these datasets into GenoMed4All's future platform for model training and a potential joint workshop on the core concepts underlying our vision for Federated Learning.

4.3.5 Discussing collaboration avenues and key synergies with SYNTHEMA

Cross-European collaboration and knowledge sharing is one of the core principles of all EU funded projects, and even more so when more than one initiative is dedicated to the same area of work, as it's the case for SYNTHEMA and GenoMed4All: two projects focusing on the use of Artificial Intelligence within the context of healthcare and personalised medicine applied to hematological rare diseases.

While GenoMed4All is building a secure and trustworthy Federated Learning platform to pool genomic health data via AI algorithms, SYNTHEMA aims to generate reliable and high-quality synthetic data that can shape new virtual patients and further enhance diagnostic capacity, assess treatment options and predict outcomes in rare hematological diseases.

On 28th September 2023, both consortiums hosted a joint meeting to explore synergies and gain a better understanding about the connections of their work, and the potential transfer of knowledge between the projects. Through 5 rapid-fire talks, representative partners involved in both projects presented their latest achievements for SYNTHEMA and GenoMed4All — and how they feed into each other. The outcomes and insights from this workshop were collected to craft a recap blog post on our website ([here](#)).

4.4 GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large

The GenoMed4All training program has been created in collaboration with ERN-EuroBloodNet. The initial definition was presented in **D8.2 – GenoMed4All training programme definition**, submitted back in December 2022. Since then, intense planning has followed to validate the main topic for the training curriculum, nominate speakers, fix a calendar, define an adequate dissemination plan and finally, launch the program. For these initial discussions, a [Technical/Scientific Educational Committee](#) was also established.

GenoMed4All's training program has been structured in two waves:

- ❑ **Wave #1– GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on AI in hematology for the public-at-large:** this first wave began in September 2023 and finished in November 2023. It comprised 4 webinar sessions (around 1h 30 min each) and acted as an introduction to GenoMed4All and its core areas for a wider, non-specialized audience. Sessions covered the topics around precision medicine in hematology, use cases challenges in MDS, MM and SCD, data standardization and linkage and data integration and analysis
- ❑ **Wave #2:** this second wave is currently in the planning stage. It is meant to address a highly specialized, advanced audience, both healthcare professionals and patient advocates. Key topics to consider include GenoMed4All's onboarding strategy, showcase of key results on the platform and the project's future exploitation and long-term sustainability.

So far, a dedicated section on our website ([Training](#)) was created to promote this first training wave, including links to each session's registration forms, detailed information and links to the full edited recordings. The same platform will be replicated for the launch of Wave #2.

Welcome!

The GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational Program on **Artificial Intelligence and its applications in hematology** targets the public-at-large and aims to increase awareness on the cutting-edge advances of Artificial Intelligence for the diagnosis, treatments and follow-up of three different rare hematological clinical domains. The growing role of Artificial Intelligence is thus displayed in improving care and accelerating patients' management via personalized medicine.

This program consists of a cycle of 4 webinars provided by key experts in the application of Artificial Intelligence in the field of Rare Hematological Diseases. Each webinar is a live session where interaction among speakers and the audience is encouraged during the closing Q&A session.

[OUR EDUCATIONAL COMMITTEE](#)

The Program

GenoMed4All & ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational program on **Artificial Intelligence in hematology for public-at-large** will provide an overview of GenoMed4All's mission and relevant applications of Artificial Intelligence in biomedicine. Different aspects of those approaches will be tackled, starting from the precision medicine definition, problem solving approach and the use of multi omics (Genomics, Metabonomics, Proteomics, Radionics) in clinical research. The following use cases will be presented: Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS), Sickle Cell disease (SCD) and Multiple myeloma (MM). Strategies for data standardization and cross-border linkage of repositories. Finally, it will be addressed the Artificial Intelligence multi-modal approaches for diagnosis, early risk assessment and disease progression prediction. Mentioned topics are divided into those 4 different sessions, as can be seen below.

SESSION #1 - GENOMED4ALL & ERN-EUROBLOODNET FOR PRECISION MEDICINE IN HEMATOLOGY

SESSION #2 - USE CASES CHALLENGES: MDS, SCD & MM

Speakers
 Matteo Della Porta (Humanitas Research Hospital)
 Mar Meko Pereira (Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca)
 Raffaella Colombatti (Università di Padova)
 Marina Martello (Università di Bologna)

When?
 September 27, 2023
 From 12:30 PM to 2:00 PM CET

[REVISIT THIS SESSION](#)

SESSION #3 - DATA STANDARDIZATION & LINKAGE (STANDARDS & FEDERATION)

SESSION #4 - DATA INTEGRATION & ANALYSIS (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Figure 39. GenoMed4All website – Training

4.5 Associate Members Onboarding Handbook

The purpose of this handbook is to expand GenoMed4All's reach and help onboard new members to the platform. This ambition ties into our long-term vision for sustainability and is crystalized through a series of key points in GenoMed4All's so-called manifesto, a series of key goals which make up the core of our value proposition for Associate Members:

- ❑ **Fighting against data scarcity and fragmentation:** despite the existence of national collaborative groups for many HDs –some of them cooperating at EU level– national approaches for the clinical management and research of hematological disease are often ineffective, especially for rarest conditions due relative low number of patients per disease, and the high number of unconnected clinical entities with relevant data.
- ❑ **Advocating for data quality and reliability:** the amount of data is key in the advance towards providing solutions to unmet needs, and data quality and reliability is something GenoMed4All is looking to provide solutions for. Automatic tools are helping the pre-processing of information, and AI algorithms to semi-automatically curate the data.
- ❑ **Leading the way in distributed scaling up:** scaling up the research in a distributed manner will as well ease the collaboration: there is no need to upload data to any central place or cloud, data will be always kept onsite at the hospital or clinical site; a secure and trustworthy option.
- ❑ **Pushing the boundaries on pooling real-world data from multiple sources:** advances towards research in rare diseases can be unlocked if there's a solution to pool and contribute with high quality data. Data can be of any clinical kind, multi-omics (e.g. radiomics, genomics, metabolomics, etc.), and in the near future the system will be able to incorporate more real world data (on PROMs, fitness information, nutrition, environment...) to the studies.
- ❑ **Building and nurturing an active community:** having access to a network of researchers per disease, to drive strong shared publications, discuss funding opportunities and clinical trials and support researchers' careers.

The Associate Members Onboarding Handbook is a 5-part manual that follows the structure below:

- ❑ **Part I – About GenoMed4All:** this first section is meant to present the project's key facts and figures. It includes a general introduction, GenoMed4All's context, vision, targets and the team behind the idea, together with an overview on how we approach AI for the diagnosis, prognosis and treatment of hematological diseases.
- ❑ **Part II – Our commitment to advance rare disease research:** this second part has been conceived as a positioning statement highlighting our commitment to rare disease research. As such, it covers our use cases in MDS, SCD and MM, with its main challenges and clinical aims; showcase the importance of Federated Learning as a key enabler and details GenoMed4All's proposed platform modes for clinicians and researchers.

- ❑ **Part III – Becoming an Associated Member:** this section reads as a call-to-action for another like-minded projects, initiatives and individuals to join. It focuses on our value proposition for Associate Members, outlining key actions and collaboration areas.
- ❑ **Part IV – Specific requirements for onboarding:** here we define the specific provisions for contributing data and present the steps of the onboarding process. This includes: the platform’s architecture, data dictionaries, timeline and requirements.

Figure 40. GenoMed4All's Onboarding Handbook

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has been presented primarily as a periodic update on GenoMed4All's Dissemination and Communication strategy and the current state-of-play after the project's first 18 months of operation, and has been subsequently amended to include all relevant updates up to M36.

During this period, several major milestones were accomplished: the project's visual identity and key branding assets have been produced, main digital channels for the project have been set up and consolidated, and the first joint efforts on the publication and promotional fronts have successfully come into fruition.

As a consequence, GenoMed4All now has a harmonized, easily recognizable brand identity to rely on, which has in turn allowed us to build a solid online presence and maintain regular interactions with a tight-knit, growing community around AI and its wider ramifications in hematology and ultimately, the healthcare realm.

GenoMed4All's Communication and Dissemination strategy is a living creature that requires a collaborative, dynamic and constant effort from the consortium and as such, also evolves in parallel with the project itself. Ultimately, this means that all **outreach materials, channels and tools** described in this document will be carefully revised and fine-tuned to adequately reflect the project's journey and its accomplishments.

Naturally, as the project goes on and progressively reaches a higher degree of maturity, emphasis will shift in favor of **more targeted dissemination (scientific) activities**. As a consequence, both **publishing and networking efforts** have intensified. This has been a unique opportunity to capitalize on our digital channels to maximize the project's reach and visibility.

Furthermore, these efforts also feed into the already on-going work devoted to drafting a tailored **business plan, value proposition and tentative service portfolio** for GenoMed4All, which has been further explored in deliverable **D9.3 – Interim Impact Assessment, Exploitation and Sustainability Report**.

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